

Data Archival and publishing: focus meeting report

Document track

Date	Name	Comment
April 19, '21	Irina van Dijk (UMC Utrecht), Nico Poppelier (UMC Utrecht)	draft version
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Target audience

This report summarizes the focus meeting for Data Archival and Publishing, co-organized by the Data Stewardship Community of Health-RI, SURF, the Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences (DTL) and the University Medical Centre Utrecht. It is targeted at participants of this focus meeting and others interested in data archival and publishing.

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Meeting summary

Why

In the Data Stewardship Community meetings held by Health-RI, healthcare data stewards from different institutes come together to discuss a broad range of research support issues and solutions. In one of these meetings, we observed that all Health-RI partner institutes were working on one or more aspects of data publishing and archival. To prevent that every institute needs to reinvent the wheel, we organized a focus meeting on this topic.

Aim

The primary goal of the focus meeting was to have an open discussion about data publishing and archival. By sharing current developments around publishing and archival, we aimed to identify good practices that can be used by the partners of Health-RI. Another goal was to develop ideas for collaborations in this field in the near future. At the end of the meeting we made first steps to translate these ideas into concrete actions.

Program

12:15 - 12:30 Virtual coffee

12:30 - 12:40 Welcome and Purpose by Irina van Dijk (UMC Utrecht)

12:40 - 14:00 Invited speakers:

- [Edwin Geleijn \(Amsterdam UMC\): "My struggle collecting data for Covid-19 revalidation"](http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4917277)
- [Margreet Bloemers/Bas de Waard \(ZonMw\): "What we are asking as a funder, and why"](http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4917324)
- [Nico Poppelier \(UMC Utrecht\): "The UMC Utrecht approach to data repository"](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4835795)
- [Hylke Koers \(SURF\): "How SURF facilitates FAIR data"](http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4922486)

14:00 - 14:10 Break

14:10 - 14:15 Explanation breakout sessions

14:15 - 14:45 Parallel breakout session

14:45 - 15:10 Reporting back from the breakouts

15:10 - 15:40 Time for plenary discussion

15:40 - 15:50 Evaluation and next steps

15:50 - 16:00 Closing

Date

25 March 2021

Location

Zoom (online)

Chair

Irina van Dijk, UMC Utrecht

Facilitator

Mijke Jetten, Health-RI/DTL

Attendance

The following organisations were present:

AmsterdamUMC, DANS/KNAW, DTL, Erasmus MC, EUR, Health-RI, Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, LUMC, Luxembourg Center for Systems Biomedicine, Lygature, NKI, Noordwest Ziekenhuisgroep, OLVG, Radboud UMC, SURF, UMC Utrecht, University of Basel, University of Groningen, University of Tartu, University of Twente, Utrecht University, Utrecht University of Applied Sciences, Wageningen University & Research, ZonMw

Presentation summary

The focus meeting started with four short presentations that highlighted different perspectives on data archival and publishing. The first two presentations highlighted '*problems*' around data archival and publishing, followed by two presentations on possible '*solutions*'. This chapter summarizes the key points of all presentations. Link to the presentation slides can be found in the Program.

Presentation 1: Amsterdam UMC

Edwin Geleijn is performing a text-mining study on Electronic Health Record (EHR) data, including unstructured text (prose written by healthcare workers). He aims to predict the rehabilitation outcomes of Covid-19 patients. Therefore, he needs a lot of data from various sources (EHRs of different hospitals and other healthcare institutes, such as general practitioners), including linking of data (data from multiple sources but corresponding to one individual). He began his research project in the first quarter of 2020. Several hospitals are enthusiastic to participate, but precisely defining the necessary data turns out to be difficult.

Model: similar to the [Personal Health Train](#). Each participant prepares the necessary data and runs the algorithm in its own infrastructure. The results are linked by a trusted third party. Privacy issues are important: discussions about opt-in versus opt-out, pseudonymising data via a trusted third party (TTP), data transfer agreements (DTA), data privacy impact assessment (DPIA), safe storage, secured servers and prevention of data leakage.

Milestones: many participants/hospitals on board. However, none of them have submitted data yet! It shows that data sharing is pretty complicated and that you need to take care of a lot of things to actually bring data together.

Presentation 2: ZonMw

ZonMw is a Dutch funder for health research and development. In the presentation, Margreet Bloemers highlighted the importance of adequate Research Data Management (RDM) and FAIR data as enablers for verification of research results and data reuse. Funders are one of the driving forces for FAIR data, because funders set requirements for FAIR data in grant proposals. In addition, funders can have a facilitating role, since they can enable new developments and have connections with many parties. For example, for Covid-19 data metadata templates and a data portal were established together by Health-RI, GO FAIR, DTL and ZonMw.

ZonMw monitors outcomes of funded research projects, including the writing of a data-management plan (DMP), but they also heavily rely on procedures and infrastructure of the individual institutes to help make data FAIR. ZonMw realizes that it is important not to ask too much from researchers, since it also depends on the pace of the institutes. She is aware of the thoughts of "the exhausted

researcher”: ‘the funder asks so much, I need to tick some more boxes’. The purpose of the talk was to show that funder requirements are done for the benefit of the researchers as well!

One of the main questions is what data should be archived? Margreet explained that ZonMw encourages researchers to be critical and to only select data for archival that are needed for verification and follow-up research. What to archive exactly, depends on type of research, research community, legal requirements, etcetera.

Margreet focused in her presentation on the ‘why’ and would like to discuss ‘the ‘what’. Furthermore, she emphasized that researchers should consult experts in their own institute to learn *how* to archive/publish. For example, institutes can help researchers to add persistent identifiers and to find a good archive with a Core Trust Seal. That helps researchers to create FAIR data, and funders ask that/rely on that. Note, as a funder: stand still for a moment, don’t go too quick/ask too much from the researcher.

Considerations: who is responsible for the quality of the data; who are the experts in the institutes, services etcetera; feasibility; costs/who is going to pay: during the project can be covered by funding, but after the project (long-term archiving) should be paid by the institute? This highlights why we should discuss what data to keep, and the return on (time) investment for the researcher.

Presentation 3: UMC Utrecht

Present situation: publishing (sharing) datasets is rarely done, nothing is archived adequately at the end of a study (files stay in the folder where they were created and used), and finding older data is difficult. Conclusions of phase 1 of the project that is currently running at UMC Utrecht is that two facilities are needed.

1. Internal archive: all materials related to a study must be archived for 15, 25 or even 30 years (legislation) and preferably ‘on premise’ due to the confidential nature of certain types of data, but also the cost involved with large-scale data storage by third parties.
2. External repository: for visibility and sharing with everyone.

What software solutions are available? There is commercial archiving software, open source archiving software, and open source repository software, and there are also repository providers. In the project at UMC Utrecht, we asked ourselves: which ones shall we evaluate and how do we evaluate? UMC Utrecht used a set of criteria developed by an RDA interest group. This was applied to a list of suitable candidates. Pilot 1, with YODA, was unsuccessful. Pilot 2, with Archivematica and Dataverse, was successful. Advantages of these software components:

- Archivematica: adequate archiving on file-level, detailed logging, extensive web interface
- Dataverse (including Dataverse-NL): mature metadata model, clear interface for users and administrators

Important conclusion: no single software package does both (internal archive and external repository), so you always need a combination of two.

Two processes are being implemented. Process 1: during research, for each publication select and archive the files relevant to that publication, publish this on DataverseNL, which also results in a DOI. Process 2, the closing of a project/study, archive *all* material relevant to that study or project.

This is a big change for researchers and data stewards! We need to educate users, train data stewards, and start small, e.g. with one or two specific research groups, and then slowly increase the number of research groups or departments.

FAIR, findability: key ingredients are the metadata model of Dataverse and the automatic assignment of a DOI. Study by the UU: how findable is my data in real life? Very findable, is the conclusion. The report by Utrecht University will (hopefully) be available in Q2 2021 .

FAIR, accessibility: access restriction and access requests are possible via Dataverse. However, there is a limitation of file size (10 GB per file), which could lead to datasets with 'holes' (large data files stay on premise and are not in Dataverse, which limits accessibility). But aside from these issues, Dataverse is a really good solution!

Presentation 4: SURF

In the form of a pilot, SURF offers a YODA service for Dutch universities. YODA was developed at Utrecht University (UU), and is based on iRODS. SURF has a rich history in storage solutions, data processing (HPC) as well as data management. Solutions are available for the entire data life cycle, mapped to the research life cycle.

YODA supports the entire data life cycle (data storing, sharing, archiving & publication), and therefore supports both researchers and data stewards. YODA is very scalable. SURF now brings YODA, initially developed by the UU, to the bigger community, to other institutions in the Netherlands.

YODA offers a research folder in the active phase of research, and two interfaces to work with data. At any point a researcher thinks it is necessary to archive, s/he can archive a selected folder in the so-called Vault. In this process, metadata has to be supplied via a web form. YODA verifies that the metadata is complete. When this is done, the package is moved to the vault and becomes immutable. You publish data via a DOI (using Datacite) and this is indexed by search engines.

The role of SURF: iRODS expertise is available at SURF. Currently the YODA service is in pre-production phase, and production phase is expected for end 2021 (after a go/no go decision). SURF has a dual role: service provider for YODA, but also establishes and organizes collaboration between institutions.

Break-out sessions

After the four presentations, the participants were divided into 5 break-out rooms. In these break-out rooms, subgroups discussed the following topics.

1. Do you recognize the problems sketched in the above presentations? Are there additional problems, not sketched yet?
2. Do you recognize the solutions sketched in the above presentations? Are they applicable in your own organization? Are there additional solutions, not sketched yet?
3. What steps can we take together to move forward, to solve the problems together? And to implement the solutions together?

Discussion summary

Afterwards, everyone came back to the central session to report insights from the break-out rooms and to have a plenary discussion. We summarize the discussions below.

Metadata: available schemas, generic or specific schemas, which one to apply, making metadata mandatory right from the start. Metadata at column level (variable level) makes searching appropriate data easier. Also important are persistent identifiers, e.g. DOI for articles and datasets, ORCID for people.

Collaboration in the area of RDM support, e.g. on one campus. National training, awareness program, guidelines etcetera. Single source for information about rules and regulations. A good example is the FAIRplus-project of IMI working on a [FAIRplus Cookbook](#) with recipes that help with the fairification of datasets that is available to everyone.

Availability of data stewards. How do we fund this? Costs for long-term data handling, including archiving, are not covered by external funding. Researchers who apply for a grant are not always

aware what type of data stewardship costs can be covered. It is an ongoing process: there will be a need for more and more data stewards. We need to have trained people with expertise. We advocate both data-oriented researchers as well as research-oriented data stewards, as the future normal.

Finding data: within the institute, outside the institute. Is a dataset open or closed?

Solutions are scattered, every institute looks for its own solutions. All in development. More (inter)national collaboration is wanted. Think about priorities, joint efforts, national working groups.

Credit researchers for practicing FAIR and Open Science, i.e. for archiving and publishing (sharing) well-organised and documented datasets. Is it sufficient to publish metadata or should researchers publish complete replication packages? And keep in mind: rewarding is better than pushing.

Interoperability between analysis environments (including DRE and VRE) and data repositories/archives. Which solutions are available to researchers? Changes needed at the level of organizational culture. Not only find solutions in the technical way, also find ways to connect to people to make a culture change.

Personal Health Train in relation to FAIR. Importance of aggregators. Data collection for Covid-19 research is a good example of the necessity. Doing it right from the start costs time and money. Doing it right at a later point in time costs even more.

Follow-up

During the meeting, we identified several potential follow-up steps for collaboration: systems, metadata, people and workflows or policies. One concrete follow-up step proposal is to write a white paper with use cases with current issues with archiving and publishing. These use cases would provide valuable input to a national strategy to solve these issues.

Action research: work on one use case in actual practice, and see what obstacles you encounter. Develop a workflow as you go along.